

A conversation Blended Course

Manal Shammout

Manalshammout1980@gmail.com

A conversation Blended Course

This paper aims at designing a course that depends on constructive alignment and didactic principles.

Course Setting

This course is designed for Arab International University [AIU] students which is a private university located in Daraa, Syria. It is an English conversation course for advanced learners. This course is credited i.e. it has two-hour credit from the overall number of hours they have to achieve before graduation and the total mark affects the students' GPA.

This course relies on the blended learning mode i.e. it will be conducted partially in a face to face classroom and partially online. AIU classrooms are well-equipped and they use the open box or semi-circular layout which fosters interaction and communication. In addition, they have state-of-the-art computers, speakers and projectors which guarantees the success of any course. The first part of the course is taught in classes at university and the second part is at home using Zoom application and Moodle. Students just need a laptop, speakers, microphone, zoom app and a constant Internet connection. As for Moodle, students have already had accounts on Moodle and they know how to deal with it.

By the end of the course, students will have to take two exams: midterm and final as well as a group-work project presentation. The exams will assess their abilities to speak English appropriately in different cultural, social and academic contexts taking into their consideration other paralinguistic features like body language, tone of voice

The course will depend mainly on worksheets that include different types of activities. Each session will tackle a different topic and function like roleplaying, debate, free discussion, problem-solving... . The students' major, level, interest and age will be taken into account.

Target Group

This course targets students from all faculties at university: Dentistry, Pharmacy, IT, Architecture, Civil Engineering, Fine Art, Business Administration and Law. The number of students will range from 20-25 aged between 18-22 and they will be male and female. All students have done a placement test that determined their actual level in English.

There is a pre-requisite for joining this course which is all students should be either upper intermediate i.e. exempted from course because their English level is higher than intermediate or they have finalized the intermediate level.

Students will be familiar with the course nature which mainly depends on interactive tasks such as group discussion, roleplaying, debating, problem solving, negotiating... .

Students belong to different cultures according to the place they were raised in and the type of school they joined. Three different cultures are noticed:

1. Syrian students who joined public schools in Syria. They belong to the stereotypical culture and academic system here.
2. Syrian students who joined private schools in Syria. They are more open-minded and they are familiar with foreign culture and international academic system.
3. Syrian students who joined private schools abroad. They belong to the culture and academic system of that country.

Teacher's Competences

For teachers to be successful teaching this course, they should have the skills and knowledge. To maximize student learning, teachers must have expertise in a wide-ranging array of competencies in an especially complex environment where hundreds of critical decisions are required each day (Jackson, 1990). There are four competences the teacher of this course should have:

Subject -Related

Teachers should be highly qualified and make sure that students understand what has been taught, become fluent in new material, and can generalize what they learn to novel situations they encounter in the future. Teachers should be responsible for determining the topics to be discussed, the type of material, the design of activities, the criteria for success, the evaluation of student acquisition (Archer & Hughes, 2011; Knight, 2012).

Moreover, teachers should have an encyclopedic knowledge since the course is a conversation course and students might discuss any subject. Teachers should have a computer literacy and expert in using online applications like Zoom and a platform like Moodle.

Social Skills

There are many social skills teachers should possess:

- Teachers should be very sociable and have the ability to be a very successful communicator with students orally, in writing, and in gestures, tone of voice and online.
- Teachers should understand and respect differences and have the ability to manage contradiction and arguments.

- Teachers should encourage cooperation and teamwork.
- Teachers should guarantee fun to kill boredom.
- Teachers should have to ability to make all students involved.

Personal Skills

Teachers should be inspiring who can get all students involved profoundly by stimulating their interest in learning, motivating love for learning, listening to others and being flexible and capable of coping with new situations (Attakorn, Tayut, Pisitthawat, & Kanokorn, 2014).

Didactic- Methodological Skills

In this course, a variety of teaching strategies should be used taking into account the following points:

- Using different theory every lesson to kill boredom.
- Making the learning objectives very clear in the beginning of every lesson
- Taking the students’ learning styles into consideration when designing the activities.

Course Objectives

Students who successfully complete this course will be able to:

- Participate more confidently in formal and informal conversations.
- Understand the importance of non-verbal communication.
- Use common phrases and idioms in conversations.
- Question, state opinions, ask for clarification & offer suggestions effectively.
- Participate in academic and everyday discussions with confidence following cultural norms.
- Use digital tools and gain digital knowledge.
- Meet alone and be autonomous learners by moderation the sessions themselves.
- Notice the importance of group work themselves.

Teaching content

The course will be planned according to constructive alignment. This course needs 8 sessions. Each session lasts for two hours weekly. There is an online part where students have to submit group projects and presentations by the end of this course using Zoom and uploaded on Moodle.

Week	Learning Outcomes	Forms of Assessment &	Content & Didactic
------	-------------------	-----------------------	--------------------

		Evaluation	Methods
1	Students will be able to <u>role play</u> any situation related to the topic of <u>music</u> like designing a musical festival, learn many new words, communicate effectively, manipulate and control voice and body language appropriately. Do a debate activity	Visual examination by the teacher for the accuracy (grammar, vocabulary)	Design activities from the perspective of learning theories. In each session a different theory is taken into account. Distribute chocolate to those who come early and ask late comers to bring chocolate (Behaviorism)
2	Students will be able to discuss in groups the topic “Healthy lifestyle” and express their opinion with reasons.	Asking students to take notes of their friend’s mistakes and discuss it in groups trying to correct them.	Revising vocabs of the previous lesson by playing with the ball and music. We move the table from one to one and when the music stops we ask the student with the ball a question (cognitivism) Prepare a video by students as part of a campaign to raise awareness towards healthy lifestyle
First online session			
3	Students will be able to discuss in groups the topic “Business” and negotiate the problems in specific situations presented on cards trying to find a solution.	Write students ‘mistakes on board without mentioning their names and asking them to come and correct them with a different colour.	Making a game (bingo, puzzle, hidden word, naught and cross) of revising vocabularies.(cognitivism) Act the roles on the card for negotiation
4	The exam assesses one of the previous topics and functions	Midterm exam is out of 25 divided into 5 marks for each (fluency, accuracy, body language, content, tone of voice)	Let the student who got the highest mark prepare an activity for the next lesson and call him the honor student (Behaviorism) Constructing a graph to illustrate certain information.
Second online session			
5	Students will be able to plan a tour after discussing questions related to the topic “Travelling”. Then play a	A <i>JCU</i> marking rubric	Have the students create an effective learning game themselves. Solve problems or answer questions listed on the

	role trying to solve problems connected with travelling on cards.		board. Have students demonstrate procedures in front of class. (cognitivism)
6	Students will be able to design a video clip for an advertisement about a certain product or service.	Focusing on the tone of voice and its role in communicating a message.	Perform or write a scenario demonstrating themes or illustrating specific ideas (cognitivism) Having students develop a questionnaire to group or gather information at hand. Creating a pros and cons list (cognitivism)
Third online session			
7	Students will be able to talk about their favourite TV show. Then they act an episode of their own tv show	Focusing on the body language and its role in communicating a message.	Simulations, role playing like acting in a cookery show, being a presenter interviewing celebrities (constructivism)
8	Function: debating	Final Exam is out of 50 divided into 10 marks for each (fluency, accuracy, body language, content, tone of voice)	Debate For/ against in pairs
Final online session A marking rubric is out of 25 for the group presentation online			

Each session will be designed using the following didactic lesson plan.

	Timing & Phase	Learning Outcomes & Teaching aims	Content & Terminology	Didactic Method & Tasks	Media & Material	Evaluation Method & Tasks
Explain	8-8.30 warm up 8.30-9 acquiring skills/ functions 9-9.30 applying the new knowledge 9.30-10 evaluation	What we intend to do In each session Express opinions agree/ disagree Compare and contrast Talk about a certain topic Design and act Find reasons to convince your partner/group Debate	Elicit information Explain terms Present new words Be accurate Give clear instructions Let students define,	Mingle and ask and answer questions Think-Pair-Share Exchange ideas with a partner Produce your video clip/ tv show/ music	Worksheets, videos, cards	One Minute paper The Muddiest point Chain notes (Angelo & Cross, 1993)

		Summarize and report your group ideas being the spokesperson (Kennedy,2007)	explain, create, design, ask and report...	festival Design activities using motivational tactics A, R, C, S (Keller, 2009)		
Didactic principle	Phase orientation	Learning outcomes in constructive alignment	Didactic reduction Motivational design	Motivational design Learner orientation & activation	Visualization principles	Formative evaluation CAT

Online part

25 students will be divided into groups of five and each group will be assigned a project to do. The assignment will be discussed via Zoom and uploaded on Moodle. We will meet four times during the semester.

- The first time is to discuss the tasks, topics, a role for each student and choose a name for the group. For example, the first group belong to the faculty of information technology so they will be called Robots. Those robots have to find an interesting topic related to their major and each works on a part. Then they meet without the teacher and coordinate things.
- In The second time, they have to do the first rehearsal and give them a feedback for things and points to be amended.
- In the third time, they meet aloud and amend the notes given by the teacher.
- The last time is for doing the final project filmed .

An example of a project plan will be like the following:

Group name	Robots
Topic	Black holes
Function	A documentary with interviews
Roles	Presenter, astronomer, astrologist, physicist, Stephen Hawking

	Student 1	Student 2	Student 3	Student 4	Student 5
Role	Presenter	astronomer	astrologist	physicist	Stephen Hawking
Function	Present the case	Discuss the topic from his point of you	Discuss the topic from his point of you	Discuss the topic from his point of you	Wrap up things

This is an example of a lesson worksheet 1

1. Make some sentences about the music cloud introducing the topic.

2. Find Someone Who

.....Listens to rock music

.....used to play a musical instrument but gave up

.....goes to rock or pop concerts regularly

.....thinks they can't sing

.....listens to different music than they did five years ago

.....says they can sing

.....has met a famous musician

.....likes the same music as you

3. Design your dream music festival.

a. Consider the following questions:

What is the name of your festival?

Where is it?

When is it?

How often does it happen?

How long does it last for?

How much do tickets cost?

What sort of music is played?

Which famous artists/ bands will headline?

Will there be any other activities?

- b. Present your ideas to the class, explaining why you made your choices.

4. Role play

You are a famous recording artist who's had a lot of success over the years, and who's made a lot of money. But even so, you simply don't believe that people should be allowed to download music from the internet for free. You wrote it, you did the work, you recorded it, performed it and produced it. You even sometimes sing free for charity. But you think it is wrong that people can take it for nothing.

Defend yourself. OK, you have money yourself, but not all singers do, and above all it's a question of principle:

You are also defending the rights of other singers who are poor and who might lose their livelihood if their music is available for free, for anybody who wants it.

Why should musicians work for free? Nobody else works for nothing.

You think the quality of music will fall if free downloading becomes the main way of obtaining music.

Now think of some more things you can say.

You are a 19 year old music fan and a student. You love music, but you don't have a lot of spare money. For this reason, you download a lot of music from the internet. You know it's illegal, but you think this is wrong. You think music is shared by the people, and you should not have to pay for it.

But a famous musician disagrees. They ask, why should you get it for free?

You think that millionaire musicians don't need any more money from music sales.

You think that music is the voice of the people and not owned by one person.

You think that more people will be able to enjoy music if it available for free.

Now think of some more things you can say.

This is an example of a lesson worksheet 2

A Generation of Couch Potatoes

I. Do you agree or disagree with these statements?

- Young people are naturally fit and healthy and don't need much exercise.
- Eating fast food is OK if you don't eat it every day.
- Old people always say negative things about teenagers' habits.
- Sport is good fun.
- Young people don't have enough time to do sports because they have too much homework.
- Universities should make all students do at least 2 hours of PE a week.

II. How does your lifestyle compare to your grandparents' lives? Has anything changed? Discuss these topics:

- Transport
- Diet
- Home
- Spare time activities

III. Physical activities Fitness campaign

Prepare a video to support your campaign on how you can encourage a more active lifestyle at university.

Talk about the name, slogan, objectives, (4) ways and activities.

Use expressions like:

- I think we should... It might be a good idea to.... Why don't we....

TV Programs

1. Unscramble the letters to spell types of TV programs.

1. paso s _ _ _ _
2. okermave m _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _
3. skid k _ _ _ _
4. posrts s _ _ _ _ _ _
5. alitery r _ _ _ _ _ _ _
6. darycuenotm d _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _
7. drmaa d _ _ _ _ _
8. corekyo c _ _ _ _ _ _ _
9. iwfeldil w _ _ _ _ _ _ _ _
10. valert t _ _ _ _ _ _

1. What is your favorite TV show? Why?

2. Create Your Own TV Show!

Get into groups of 3 or 4 students.

You work for a big TV channel in your country. You have been asked to design and create a brand new TV show.

You have a big budget to make the show — so money is no object. But you have to come up with something original and very popular.

With your group, think of an idea for a TV show. It can be any kind of show — comedy, reality TV, sports. But it has to be unique, and it has to be interesting so that many people will watch it.

In your group, try to think of:

- the main idea of the show
- what happens in the show every week
- what TV stars you will use in your show
- will it have a live audience or prerecorded
- some other special features of the show

Once you have some ideas, act the first episode to the class. Each member of your group should play a role.

The rest of the students is the audience who should ask questions during the show.

Negotiation & Complaining

1. discuss the following questions in a group of four

- How good are you at negotiating?
- What are some good negotiation tactics?
- Do you do negotiations in your work, personal like or while shopping?
- What have you had to negotiate for in your life? (Examples: House, car, items at a bazaar)
- Do you think men or women are better at negotiations? Why?

Brainstorm: With a partner, write down reasons....

- 1) why an employee might get fired.
- 2) why a company might go bankrupt.
- 3) why a candidate might not get hired for a job at an IT company after an interview.
- 4) why a student might complain about his or her school.
- 5) why a guest might ask for a refund after staying a night in a hotel.

Role-playing : With your partner, decide who will be Student A and Student B, and then role-play the below situations. Read only your role. When you and your partner are ready, you can begin.

#1 The Office

StudentA	Your employee, StudentB, has not been performing very well recently at work. S/he has many problems (See the problems for #1 above). You have invited him/her to your office. You plan to fire him/her. Talk to him/her nicely, and let him/her know that s/he must leave at the end of the day.
StudentB	Your boss has asked you to come into his/her office. You are not sure why. Recently, you have been very stressed out. You have a new baby at home, so you can't sleep. Also, your other workmates are bad at their jobs, which makes it hard for you to do your job.

#2 The Company

StudentA	You are the owner of a toy company. You have been on vacation for 6 months, and now you are back. You have arranged a meeting with the company CEO. Talk with him/her. Ask him/her how the company is doing.
StudentB	You are the CEO of a toy company. The company has been doing very poorly recently (see the problems for #2 above). The company is going to go bankrupt very soon. Now, the owner of the company wants to talk with you. Go to his/her office and talk with him/her.

#3 The Interview

StudentA	You interviewed a candidate for a job at your IT company last week. She didn't get the job (see reasons for #3 above). Now, you are at your office, and she has come in to talk with you.
StudentB	You had an interview last week at an IT company. Although you were the perfect person for the job, you didn't get the job. You are very angry. You think that you didn't get the job because of

	discrimination (for example, because you are a woman, a foreigner, etc). You have decided to go to the company today. Talk with the hiring manager (the interviewer), and find out why you weren't hired!
--	---

#4 At School

StudentA	You are the academic director of a school. A student has just knocked on your door. Invite him/her in, and talk with him/her.
StudentB	You are a student. You are at school. You have had many problems with your school (see reasons for #4 above). You have decided to go to the academic director's office to complain. Knock on his door and ask to speak with him/her.

#5 The Hotel

StudentA	You had a horrible stay at your hotel last night (see reasons for #5 above). Go downstairs and complain to the front desk clerk. You want a refund!
StudentB	You are the front desk clerk at a 5 star hotel. Your hotel is amazing. Everyone loves it. You at the front desk now and a guest has come down to talk with you.

These are examples of quiz 1

Sample A

- You are going to work with a group of four and plan a trip to a musical festival. Consider the following questions:
 - Where is the festival?
 - When is the festival?
 - How will you get there?
 - Where will you stay?
 - How long will you stay?
 - What will you do at the festival?
- Give a short presentation to the class about your festival plans.
- Be natural.
- Pay attention to body language, grammar and your tone of voice.

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

.....

End of Quiz 1

Sample B

- **You are going to create a new musical group or a musician identity for yourself. You will then try to get hired to play music at as many venues as you can.**

Be creative when thinking of your musical identity. Don't just copy an existing musician. Try to create your own unique musical identity. Remember that some venues (restaurant, bar, club, coffee shop, etc.) work well with specific genres of music.

Describe your band in one sentence

Genre: _____

What are your performances like? (energetic, chill, etc.)

What makes you, as a musician, special?

Why will your music be popular?

- Be natural.
- Pay attention to body language, grammar and your tone of voice.

End of Quiz 1

Sample C

- With your partner make a conversation comparing between two different kinds of music.
- Answer the following questions:
 1. Talk about similarities and differences.
 2. Which one is your favorite? Why?
 3. Does it have a negative or positive impact?
 4. What kind of person would like each type?
- Be natural.
- Pay attention to body language, grammar and your tone of voice.

End of Quiz 1

Sample D

- With your partner make a conversation about a song you both adore listening to.
- Answer the following questions:
 1. What is the song?
 2. What genre is it?
 3. What is it about?
 4. Who is the singer? Why do you love him/her?
 5. How was its video clip? Discuss it .
 6. What kind of person would like this song?
- Sing part of it.
- Be natural.
- Pay attention to body language, grammar and your tone of voice.
-

Rubric for evaluating and marking the quiz

Fluency	Accuracy	Tone of voice	Body language	Message delivered
5	5	5	5	5

End of Quiz 1

Reflective evaluation questions

1. Why did you like to join this optional course?
2. What does the course add to your language?
3. Would you recommend other students to join this course? Why?

Peer feedback

Rasha Al-Dahhan

Ula Al-Mujjaber

Ranwa Khorsheed

Bibliography

Angelo, T. A., & Cross, K. P. (1993). *Classroom assessment techniques: A handbook for college teachers*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass Publishers.

Archer, A. L., & Hughes, C. A. (2011). *Explicit instruction: Efficient and effective teaching*. New York, NY: Guilford Publications.

Attakorn, K., Tayut, T., Pisitthawat, K., & Kanokorn, S. (2014). Soft skills of new teachers in the secondary schools of Khon Kaen Secondary Educational Service Area 25, Thailand. *Procedia—Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 112, 1010–1013.

Keller, J. M. (2009). *Motivational Design for Learning and Performance: The ARCS Model Approach*. Springer Science & Business Media, New York, USA, p. 45, Table 3.1

Kennedy, D. (2007). *Writing and using learning outcomes: A practical guide*. University College Cork, Quality Promotion Unit. Retrieved from <http://www.cmepius.si/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/A-Learning-Outcomes-Book-D-Kennedy.pdf>

Jackson, P. W. (1990). *Life in classrooms*. New York, NY: Teachers College Press.